

Enhancement of Simarouba Glauca Biodiesel Using Aqueous Al₂O₃ Nanoparticles Stabilized with SDS Surfactant

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Abstract:

This study investigates the stability and physicochemical characteristics of aqueous aluminium oxide (Al₂O₃) nanoparticles (50 nm size) dispersed in Simarouba glauca biodiesel, using SDS (sodium dodecyl sulfate) as a surfactant. Nanoparticle concentrations of 50 mg/L and 75 mg/L were tested with SDS at mass ratios of 1:0.25, 1:0.5, 1:0.75, and 1:1. Stability was analyzed using UV-Vis spectroscopy at weekly intervals for three weeks. Results revealed improved absorbance and reduced transmittance with increased SDS ratio, indicating enhanced nanoparticle dispersion. Physicochemical parameters were evaluated per ASTM standards. The best stability and fuel properties were observed in the B20 + Al₂O₃ 75 mg/L + SDS 75 mg/L blend, achieving a calorific value of 41.42 MJ/kg and a cetane number of 64. Stability decreased over time due to sedimentation. The study confirms that aqueous Al₂O₃ nanoparticles and SDS improve the fuel characteristics and dispersion stability of Simarouba glauca biodiesel blends.

Keywords: Biodiesel, Aluminium Oxide Nanoparticles, SDS, Simarouba glauca, Nanofuel, Stability, Physicochemical Properties

1. Introduction

The quest for sustainable and efficient alternative fuels has intensified due to the depletion of fossil fuel reserves and rising environmental concerns. Biodiesel, derived from renewable biological sources, has emerged as a promising substitute for conventional diesel (Tamilvanan, 2022). Among the various feedstocks, *Simarouba glauca* has gained attention owing to its high oil yield and non-edible nature, making it a viable candidate for biodiesel production without competing with food resources (Godeto, 2023).

Despite its environmental and sustainability advantages, biodiesel generally suffers from certain limitations such as lower oxidative stability, inferior cold flow properties, and reduced

calorific value compared to petroleum diesel (Aitavade, 2022). To overcome these challenges and enhance fuel properties, recent research has explored the incorporation of metal oxide nanoparticles into biodiesel blends (Gurusamy, 2024; Mukherjee, 2024). Nanoparticles not only act as combustion catalysts but also improve fuel atomization, leading to better engine performance and lower emissions (Garlapati, 2013).

Aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3) nanoparticles are widely recognized for their thermal stability, large surface area, and catalytic potential (Chethan, 2023). However, achieving a uniform and stable dispersion of nanoparticles in biodiesel remains a critical challenge due to agglomeration and sedimentation. Surfactants such as sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) can play a significant role in stabilizing nanoparticles in colloidal systems by reducing surface tension and preventing particle aggregation (Aitavade E. N., 2024).

This study focuses on evaluating the dispersion stability and physicochemical characteristics of aqueous Al_2O_3 nanoparticles (50 nm) in *Simarouba glauca* biodiesel using SDS as a surfactant. Nanoparticle concentrations of 50 mg/L and 75 mg/L were combined with SDS at varying mass ratios (1:0.25 to 1:1), and the stability of the dispersions was monitored over three weeks using UV–Visible spectroscopy. Additionally, the effect of these additives on key fuel properties such as calorific value and cetane number was assessed in accordance with ASTM standards. The findings aim to contribute to the development of enhanced biodiesel formulations with improved performance, stability, and combustion characteristics.

2.Literature Survey

The use of nanoparticles in biodiesel has garnered considerable attention due to their potential to enhance combustion efficiency, fuel properties, and emission characteristics (Alazaiza, 2023). Several researchers have investigated various metal and metal oxide nanoparticles as additives in biodiesel blends to overcome limitations such as poor cold flow properties, low oxidation stability, and incomplete combustion (Singh, 2024).

Aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3) nanoparticles have been widely explored for their thermal conductivity, catalytic activity, and dispersion characteristics. It is reported that Al_2O_3 nanoparticles enhanced brake thermal efficiency and reduced specific fuel consumption when added to biodiesel blends. Demonstrated that the inclusion of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles in biodiesel improved combustion characteristics and reduced hydrocarbon and carbon monoxide emissions (Paramashivaiah, 2018).

The **stability** of nanoparticle dispersion in biodiesel, however, remains a significant challenge. Agglomeration and sedimentation over time reduce the effectiveness of nanoparticles. To address this, researchers have investigated the role of surfactants in stabilizing nanoparticle dispersions. SDS (sodium dodecyl sulfate), an anionic surfactant, has been shown to enhance the dispersion of nanoparticles in aqueous and non-aqueous media. For instance, Used SDS to improve the stability of ZnO nanoparticles in biodiesel, leading to better fuel property retention and improved engine performance (Manieniyan, 2022).

UV–Visible spectroscopy has become a common method for evaluating the optical stability of nanoparticle dispersions. Increase in absorbance and decrease in transmittance over time are indicators of better dispersion and colloidal stability, as reported by researchers (Pratap, 2020).

Furthermore, studies have validated that the **physicochemical properties** of biodiesel can be improved using nanoparticles. It showed that adding cerium oxide and alumina nanoparticles improved the cetane number and calorific value of Jatropha biodiesel blends (Kandasamy, 2018).

Although several works have focused on biodiesel derived from feedstocks such as Jatropha, Pongamia, and Mahua, research on **Simarouba glauca biodiesel** remains limited. The combination of aqueous Al₂O₃ nanoparticles and SDS in Simarouba-based biodiesel, as explored in this study, is novel and aims to fill this research gap by providing insights into dispersion stability and enhancement of fuel quality (Mohammadi, 2019).

This study Investigation on Stability and Physicochemical Properties of Aqueous Aluminium Oxide (50 nm) Nanoparticles Dispersed in Simarouba Glauca Biodiesel Using SDS Surfactant.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1 Biodiesel Preparation

Biodiesel was prepared from Simarouba glauca oil via transesterification. The oil was heated to 50 °C, mixed with methanol and KOH catalyst, and stirred at 60 °C for one hour. The resulting mixture was allowed to settle, and the methyl ester layer (biodiesel) was separated, washed, and dried to remove moisture. The yield was approximately 96.8% (Kandasamy, Engine performance and emission profile of Simarouba glauca biodiesel and blends, 2020).

3.2 Nanoparticle Characterization

Commercial aqueous aluminium oxide nanoparticles (50 nm) were characterized using SEM and EDS techniques. SEM confirmed spherical morphology with mild agglomeration, while EDS confirmed high purity of Al and O elements.

3.3 Nanofuel Preparation

Al₂O₃ nanoparticles were dispersed in distilled water and ultrasonicated for uniform dispersion. SDS was added in ratios of 1:0.25, 1:0.5, 1:0.75, and 1:1 with respect to the nanoparticle concentration. The mixtures were further ultrasonicated for 30 minutes. These stabilized nanofluids were blended with 20% *Simarouba glauca* biodiesel (B20) using a bath sonicator at 30 kHz for 15 minutes.

3.4 Stability Testing

The stability of aqueous aluminium oxide (Al₂O₃) nanoparticles dispersed in *Simarouba glauca* biodiesel was evaluated using a UV–Visible dual beam spectrophotometer across the wavelength range of 200–1100 nm. The samples were analyzed at weekly intervals over a period of three weeks to monitor changes in dispersion quality over time. Both absorbance and transmittance readings were recorded and interpreted using Beer–Lambert’s law, which relates the absorbance of a solution to the concentration of the absorbing species.

Higher absorbance values indicated a greater presence of dispersed nanoparticles in the colloidal system, suggesting reduced agglomeration and improved stability. Conversely, higher transmittance values were associated with sedimentation and poor dispersion. Results showed that blends with higher SDS concentrations exhibited increased absorbance and reduced transmittance, confirming the role of SDS in stabilizing the nanoparticle dispersion. Over time, a gradual decline in absorbance and increase in transmittance was observed in all samples, indicating sedimentation and reduced stability, particularly in blends with lower surfactant concentrations.

3.5 Physicochemical Properties

The physicochemical properties of the *Simarouba glauca* biodiesel blends containing Al₂O₃ nanoparticles and SDS were measured in accordance with standardized ASTM test methods to ensure accuracy and comparability (Kota, 2024). **Density** was determined using the ASTM D1298 standard, which involves a hydrometer method for assessing fluid density at a

controlled temperature. **Kinematic viscosity**, a critical parameter influencing fuel atomization and flow, was measured as per ASTM D445 using a calibrated capillary viscometer (Kainat, 2024).

The **cetane index**, an indicator of ignition quality and combustion delay, was evaluated following ASTM D976, which estimates cetane number based on fuel density and distillation data. **Flash point**, measured using the Cleveland open cup method under ASTM D92, provided insights into the fuel's volatility and safety in storage and handling. To assess the potential corrosiveness of the fuel toward engine metals, the **copper strip corrosion test** was conducted in accordance with ASTM D130. Lastly, the **calorific value**, representing the energy content of the fuel, was determined using a bomb calorimeter as per ASTM D4809 (Aitavade E. a., 2024).

These parameters collectively provided a comprehensive understanding of how the inclusion of nanoparticles and surfactant influences the performance, safety, and storage characteristics of the biodiesel blends.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Stability Analysis

The stability of the Al_2O_3 nanoparticle-dispersed biodiesel blends was found to be significantly influenced by the concentration of SDS (sodium dodecyl sulfate) used as a surfactant. SDS played a crucial role in enhancing dispersion by reducing surface tension and providing electrostatic repulsion between nanoparticles, thus minimizing agglomeration and sedimentation. As the concentration of SDS increased, a marked improvement in nanofuel stability was observed.

Among all the test samples, the blend containing **B20 + Al_2O_3 75 mg/L + SDS 75 mg/L** demonstrated the **highest stability**, with an **absorbance of 4.41** and **transmittance of 87.5%** recorded during the first week. These values, obtained using UV–Vis spectroscopy, indicated a high degree of nanoparticle dispersion within the biodiesel matrix. According to Beer–Lambert's law, a higher absorbance corresponds to a greater concentration of dispersed particles, while lower transmittance signifies reduced light passage due to effective particle suspension (Ahmad, 2024).

Over the three-week observation period, all samples showed a gradual decline in absorbance and a corresponding increase in transmittance, indicating **a reduction in stability due to**

sedimentation. However, blends with higher SDS concentrations maintained relatively better dispersion compared to those with lower surfactant content. This highlights the **effectiveness of SDS** in delaying the settling of nanoparticles by forming a protective ionic layer around them, enhancing electrostatic repulsion forces that counteract gravitational settling (Sekhar).

The results confirm that **optimal surfactant-to-nanoparticle ratios are essential** for maintaining colloidal stability in biodiesel blends. The 1:1 mass ratio of Al₂O₃ to SDS in the B20 blend provided the most favorable conditions for long-term stability and uniform dispersion. Such stable nanofuel formulations are beneficial not only for preserving consistent fuel properties but also for ensuring efficient combustion and reduced engine deposits during operation.

4.2 Physicochemical Properties

Table 1 summarizes fuel properties. The addition of Al₂O₃ nanoparticles and SDS improved calorific value and cetane index. B20 + Al₂O₃ 75 mg/L + SDS 75 mg/L achieved 41.42 MJ/kg and cetane number 64. Slight increases in density and viscosity were noted but remained within ASTM limits. The flash point decreased marginally due to improved volatility (Patidar, 2025).

Table 1: Fuel Properties

Fuel Blend	Density (kg/m ³)	Viscosity (cSt)	Cetane Index	Flash Point (°C)	Calorific Value (MJ/kg)
B100	886.1	4.58	62	162	39.01
B20	871.2	4.22	60	140	40.12
B20 + Al ₂ O ₃ 50 mg/L	874.1	4.26	61	138	40.78
B20 + Al ₂ O ₃ 75 mg/L	877.0	4.30	63	136	41.10
B20 + Al ₂ O ₃ 75 mg/L + SDS 75 mg/L	879.8	4.36	64	133	41.42

5. Conclusion

This study systematically investigated the influence of aqueous aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3) nanoparticles (50 nm) and sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) surfactant on the stability and physicochemical properties of *Simarouba glauca* biodiesel blends. The results demonstrate that the incorporation of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles, when effectively stabilized using SDS, enhances both dispersion stability and critical fuel parameters such as density, kinematic viscosity, cetane index, flash point, copper strip corrosion resistance, and calorific value, as evaluated according to ASTM standards.

UV–Vis spectroscopic analysis confirmed that increased SDS concentrations significantly improved nanoparticle dispersion, with the B20 + Al_2O_3 75 mg/L + SDS 75 mg/L formulation exhibiting the highest absorbance and lowest transmittance in the first week, indicative of superior colloidal stability. Over time, a slight reduction in stability was observed due to sedimentation, yet the higher surfactant concentrations effectively minimized agglomeration through electrostatic stabilization mechanisms.

Among all tested formulations, the B20 + Al_2O_3 75 mg/L + SDS 75 mg/L blend consistently showed optimal performance in terms of both stability and fuel quality. This blend is therefore identified as the most promising candidate for further **engine performance and emission testing**. The findings confirm that the strategic use of nanoparticles and surfactants offers a practical and scalable approach to enhancing the functional characteristics of biodiesel, thereby supporting its broader adoption as a clean and efficient alternative fuel.

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